

Indian Sign Language Translator Using CNN

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Abstract – This paper main focus is to create a real-time Indian Sign Language (ISL) translator designed to overcome the gap between the deaf and hard-of-hearing population and the hearing population. By leveraging computer vision techniques and machine learning models, the system can accurately recognize a wide range of ISL gestures and translate them into corresponding text outputs in English. The application is intended to facilitate seamless communication, enhancing accessibility in various settings such as education, healthcare, and daily interactions. This solution aims to foster greater inclusion and social integration for ISL users while addressing the lack of real-time ISL translation tools in India.

Index Terms – Indian Sign Language Translator, MediaPipe, Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), Feed Forward Neural Networks, Hand Gesture Recognition.

I. INTRODUCTION

Communication is the fundamental aspect of human engagement, helping individuals to share their ideas, emotions, and information. For the deaf and hard-of-hearing community, communication with those who do not know sign language presents unique challenges, often resulting in misunderstandings and barriers to equal participation. Indian Sign Language (ISL) serves as a crucial means of communication for numerous individuals in this community, offering a rich, visual language that expresses complex ideas. However, for effective communication between ISL users and hearing individuals, a translation system is essential to bridge the language gap and enable more seamless interaction.

Technological breakthroughs in artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning have opened new opportunities for developing systems that can understand and translate sign languages into text. Machine learning models, combined with computer vision techniques, can analyse visual data, recognize gestures, and interpret meaning, providing an accurate translation of sign language in real-time. As these technologies advance, they hold the potential to greatly improve accessibility for the deaf and hard-of-hearing community, creating tools that can translate ISL and other sign languages for wider

communication. The proposed ISL translation system is designed to recognize ISL gestures through a camera, translate them into text and display the output in a form that hearing individuals can easily understand. By capturing gestures in real time, the system aims to facilitate natural conversations, allowing for faster and more accurate translation compared to traditional text-based methods. This will empower individuals in the deaf community to engage in many educational, social, and professional settings without needing a human interpreter, making communication more independent and flexible.

The development of this system involves several core modules, including gesture recognition, translation, user interface, and analytics. Each module plays a critical role in the system's overall functionality, from recognizing ISL gestures accurately to delivering clear translations in multiple languages. A user-friendly interface ensures the system is accessible, while analytics and feedback modules help refine performance over time. These components, working in tandem, create a robust solution aimed at addressing the specific needs of ISL users in their day-to-day interactions. Despite the potential of this technology, developing an ISL translation system also presents challenges, such as the need for comprehensive ISL datasets, the complexity of gestures, and the nuances of sign language. Additionally, maintaining accuracy across different regional variations of ISL and adapting the system to specific contexts or dialects are critical factors for its success. By addressing these challenges through research, data collection, and rigorous testing, the project aims to create a versatile and accurate translation system that can be widely adopted and effectively meet users' needs.

In summary, this ISL translation system aims to break down communication barriers for the hearing-impaired community in India. Through innovative technology, user-centred design, and ongoing improvements, it seeks to create a more inclusive environment for individuals who rely on sign language. The project envisions a world where language no longer limits accessibility and where ISL users have the tools to communicate seamlessly with the hearing population, fostering understanding and greater inclusivity in diverse settings.

II. RELATED WORKS

Many researchers have explored different ways to interpret sign language, using both hardware and software-based approaches. The early systems relied heavily on wearable devices like data gloves, which could capture the position and movement of the hand in real-time. While effective in some ways, these systems had limitations in terms of comfort, accuracy, and cost. The Microsoft Kinect sensor has been utilized for sign language recognition by generating depth sensor frames, where a movement is represented as a timeline of these frames. T. Pryor introduced SignAloud, a pair of gloves embedded with sensors to track hand positions and movements, enabling the conversion of gestures into speech. Similarly, R. Hait-Campbell engineered MotionSavvy, a system that employs a Windows tablet with a Leap Motion accelerator (AXLR8R) to recognize the skeletal structure of the hand and arm. Another solution, Sceptre, leverages Myo armbands, equipped with accelerometer, gyroscope, and EMG sensors for gesture recognition. While these technology-based solutions offer high accuracy, they are often costly and lack portability. In contrast, our system reduces the need for external sensors with the use of a camera of an Android smartphone.

Software-based solutions for gesture recognition include approaches based on colored gloves and skin color detection. R. Y. Wang utilized various colored gloves to make use of precise hand gesture reconstruction, though this method requires the signer to wear the gloves during every demonstration. Skin color-based solutions, on the other hand, often rely on RGB or HSV color spaces, with the latter offering better luminosity invariance. G. Awad trained SVM for skin color variation detection using the beginning frames of a video in sequence, followed by a Kalman filter to predict the coordinates of skin-colored objects, thereby lowering the search space and speeding up skin segmentation. Once the segmented hand image is obtained, A. B. J utilized rules from hand anthropometry studies relative measurements of the human anatomy to detect and remove the palm. Later, the remaining segmented image, which contained only the fingers, a skin-pixel histogram centered around the palm centroid which was then generated and provided to a decision tree classifier. A hand contour was extracted from the segmented hand image and used to fit a convex hull, identifying convexity defects to recognize fingers and determine the angles between adjacent ones. These angle-based features were then fed into an SVM for classification. Another approach employed using the distance transform, the hand centroid was identified, followed by the removal of the palm, with finger angles were utilized for classification, while Fourier Descriptors described the hand contours. These descriptors were processed using an RBF kernel for hand poses classification.

S. C. Agarwal combined geometric features, along with Histogram of Oriented Gradients (HOG) and Scale-Invariant Feature Transform key points, and used them as feature vectors. Nonetheless, the reliability of geometric features decreased significantly as the number of hand poses increased. Local Binary Patterns were also used as parameters, with Knn models trained directly on binary segmented hand images were utilized, providing high-speed performance in addition with fast indexing methods, which made it ideal for real-time applications. However, to manage changes in hand configurations effectively, a larger dataset was required. In gesture recognition, tracking the hand centroid is utilized to extract motion information. One approach involves using a Finite State Machine (FSM) where each gesture is explicitly defined. C. Y. Kao used two-hand gestures to train a Hidden Markov Model (HMM) in the context of gesture recognition, directive gestures like up, left, right, and down were defined for both hands, with a time series of paired gestures fed into the HMM for classification. C. W. Ng introduced a hybrid approach by combining HMM and Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) classifiers for gesture recognition. The HMM-based gesture recognition employed in our system draws inspiration from their methodology. Their approach used five distinct hand poses along with the same four directive gestures, creating a nine-element feature vector as input to the HMM classifier. The training process for the HMM utilized Baum-Welch formulas, which allowed for efficient parameter optimization.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Research and Requirements Gatering

A thorough review of existing datasets and literature on Indian Sign Language (ISL) gesture recognition was conducted to understand the available resources and identify gaps in the current models. Based on this research, a dataset of images representing various ISL gestures was compiled, sourced from publicly available datasets or custom collections. The dataset was analyzed to ensure it covered a wide range of gestures. Subsequently, the requirements for the model, including input dimensions, preprocessing techniques, and augmentation strategies, were established to ensure the success of the classifier.

B. Data Collection and Preprocessing

The dataset for this project consists of images representing various ISL gestures, sourced from publicly available datasets or custom collections. The images were resized to a consistent resolution (64x64 pixels) to standardize input dimensions. Additionally, pixel values scaled from a range of 0 to 1 to facilitate quicker loss-function calculation during training. Data enhancement techniques, such as rotations, flips, and translations, were adopted to diversify the training data and mitigate the occurrence of overfitting.

Figure 1. Methodology for the proposed system

C. Model Development

This model utilizes a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) due to its impact in image classification tasks. The network begins with an input layer accepting images of size 64x64 pixels. The model then employs Several convolutional layers with 32, 64, and 128 filters, succeeded by max-pooling layers that decrease spatial complexity and computational load. After feature extraction, the network uses fully connected layers to learn complex patterns, with a SoftMax activation function at the output layer provides predictions for classifying the input image into one of the ISL gestures.

D. Training the Model

Training, validation, and test sets were created from the dataset, and the model is trained with a batch size of 32 to 55 epochs approximately. The model training was halted early based on performance criteria to halt training when validation performance plateaued, preventing overfitting. The model was optimized through backpropagation using the Adam optimizer, adjusting weights to minimize the categorical cross entropy loss.

E. Evaluating and Testing

After training, the model's accuracy was evaluated on the test set. Accuracy, recall, precision, and F1-score were calculated to know how well this model classified ISL gestures. A confusion matrix was also generated to visualize misclassifications and identify which gestures the model found most challenging to recognize.

F. Results Interpretation

The model's results were analyzed using training and validation accuracy curves, as well as a confusion matrix. These visualizations helped understand the model's learning process and highlighted areas where it struggled to classify certain gestures. Recall, Precision, and F1-scores provided a more in-depth analysis of the model's performance for each section.

IV. ALGORITHMS USED

A. CNN

CNNs (Convolutional Neural Networks) are a kind of neural networks tailored for handling structured data, such as images. These are highly effective for tasks such as image recognition and labelling by learning spatial hierarchies of features, starting from basic patterns like edges to more complex objects. Images are represented as arrays of pixel values, where the dimensions depend on their resolution and colour channels:

- RGB Images: Represented as $h \times w \times 3$ (three channels for red, green, and blue).
- Grayscale Images: Represented as $h \times w \times 1$ (a single channel for intensity).

Figure 2. CNN Architecture

The fundamental core blocks of a CNN model are:

- 1) Convolutional Layers: These layers are the backbone of CNNs. They apply filters (or kernels) to the input image, scanning it by sliding the filters over and performing mathematical operations (convolution). This process helps detect basic features like edges, corners, and textures. As the data progresses through multiple convolutional layers, the network identifies increasingly complex patterns, such as shapes and objects. This allows the model to learn a hierarchy of features from low-level (edges) to high-level (parts of objects).
- 2) Activation Function: After each convolution operation, the result is passed through an activation function, commonly ReLU (Rectified Linear Unit). ReLU introduces non-linearity, enabling the network to learn complex patterns and relationships in the data.
- 3) Pooling Layers: These layers, often placed following the convolutional layers, reduce the spatial dimensions of feature maps. A common technique is max-pooling, which selects the maximum value from a group of neighboring pixels. Pooling reduces computational complexity, minimizes the chance of overfitting, and allows the model to remain invariant to slight shifts in the image.

- 4) **Fully Connected Layers:** After the convolutional and pooling layers have extracted the important features from the data, the resulting feature maps are converted into a one-dimensional vector. This vector is then fed into fully connected layers, which help the model make the final prediction. These connected layers learn high-level representations and relationships among features. The outputs from the fully connected layer are typically generated using a SoftMax activation function. for classification tasks, which assigns probabilities to each class.
- 5) **Output Layer:** This layer depends on a particular task. For labelling problems, it produces a set of probabilities for all classes are generated, and the model chooses the class with the highest probability as its final prediction.

B. Feed Forward Neural Network

This is one of the simplest types of neural networks. It consists of multiple layers of neurons, where every neuron is linked to the neurons in the previous and next layers, but there are no connections going backward. The information is passed in a single direction, from the input layer through the hidden layers to the output layer. That is why it is called "feedforward."

Figure 3. FNN Architecture

Structure of Feedforward Neural Networks

- a) **Input Layer:** The input layer is made up of neurons that take in the features of the dataset. These inputs represent the raw data or features that are fed into the network, such as pixel values in image recognition or measurements in other data processing tasks.
- b) **Hidden Layers:** There are multiple hidden layers situated in between the input and output layers, where each layer consists of neurons that apply weights to the inputs and use an activation function to process them. The neurons of these layers learn various patterns or features taken from the input data. The architecture, including the number of hidden layers and neurons in each and every layer, may vary, and these parameters are often tuned during training.
- c) **Output Layers:** This layer gives the final predictions. In multi-class classification, the SoftMax function is preferred, whereas for binary classification, a completely different function is typically utilized.

V. CONCLUSION

This research focused on developing a deep learning-based system for Indian Sign Language (ISL) gesture translation using Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) for hand tracking and gesture analysis. The project successfully implemented a model capable of accurately detecting hands and classifying ISL gestures, emphasizing the capabilities of CNNs in gesture recognition tasks. Despite challenges like

occlusions and varying hand poses, the model demonstrated good accuracy and efficiency, providing a foundation for live applications. This work contributes to the field of AI-driven gesture recognition, offering significant benefits in improving communication for the hearing-impaired community.

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